

PURE ISLAM AND ENLIGHTENMENT AGAINST IGNORANCE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will talk about those who misinterpreted Islam and the “heroes” who helped them to come to this opinion. “No matter how much a mountain is hurt with a goat's horn, the mountain cannot be hurt in the slightest” in this we should understand that no matter how much harm is done to the religion, it does not lose itself.

Key words: Qur'an, religion, faith, Muhammad, true muslim, Judgment Day.

Verily, Allah is with those who fear God and who do good.” (16:128). It is not the religion of Islam that brings trouble, but the fact that people misinterpret the knowledge they have received or follow it incorrectly. The thing is about those people who not only themselves went the wrong way (fanatics, extremists, terrorists), but also engage in calling other people to this, most often young people with weak moral and spiritual foundations, who succumb to their propaganda and false teachings. Those people who create lawlessness, who kill for religion, are in fact far from it, since religion in fact in a person's life should act as the law of morality and morality. It is by them that the true believer should be guided in his life. This is the path of love, and love, first of all, is manifested in humility and patience before the will of God. Often people hide behind religion, doing evil, but it is necessary to fight not with religion, but with those who bring evil and misfortune. Is it possible to believe those who say that they love God and their religion, but they kill, rob, and commit lawlessness? The main objects of faith in Islam: Belief in the Almighty Belief in the angels of the Almighty Belief in the Scriptures of the Almighty Belief in the Prophets and Messengers of the Almighty Belief in the predestination of the Almighty Belief in life after death. The religion that establishes a living connection between God and man is right. Islam says that the only creator of this world is the One Living God. Translated from Arabic, the word "Islam" means "surrender to the One God" or "submission." Islam is a world monotheistic Abrahamic religion. According to the Quran, Allah is the only almighty God, the Creator of all things. In Islam, he does not have a specific image and is the only object of worship for Muslims. Allah, according to Muslim dogmas, is the absolute ruler of the world, he is omniscient and omnipresent. Allah takes care of his creations and provides for them, Allah shows his mercy here. At the

same time, he severely punishes sinners and “infidels” (i.e., pagans). According to the Koran, every thing testifies to the omnipotence of Allah, his wisdom, absolute perfection, absolute unity. In Islam there is an idea according to which the end of the world will come after some time. The end of the world is inevitably followed by the so-called Judgment Day (Kiyamat). Muslims believe that there will be concrete evidence of the approach of the Day of Judgment - the disappearance of the Kaaba in Mecca, the appearance of the Dajjal (i.e. the false messiah, in the Christian tradition - the Antichrist), the second coming of Isa (i.e. Jesus Christ), etc. However, the timing of the end of the world known only to God and cannot be voiced by people. During the Day of Judgment, people will be interrogated by God, after which the righteous will go to the Gardens of Eden, and sinners and unbelievers will go to hellfire. At the same time, those Muslims who correctly and strictly fulfill all the requirements of religion will certainly find themselves in paradise. Paradise, according to Muslim ideas, is a wonderful place where the best food, clean and cool water and all kinds of sensual, carnal pleasures are found in abundance. Thus, unlike the Christian tradition, the Muslim paradise is much more sensual and mundane than the Christian one. In addition to bodily pleasures, however, there are also spiritual pleasures in Islam, the greatest of which is the contemplation of the Face of God. As for sinners and “infidels”, terrible torments await them in hell from red-hot tar and fire. Food for sinners is the fruit of the hellish tree zakkum. It is an infernal tree that grows from the "root of Gehenna", the fruits of this tree are the heads of devils. Drinking for sinners is boiling water that burns the insides. The founder of Islam - Muhammad (Muhammad, Mohammed) (570? -632) came from the Hashim clan, an influential Meccan tribe of the Qureish. Before Muhammad, the Arabs knew monotheistic religions - Judaism and Christianity (the latter - mainly in unorthodox forms: Arianism, Nestorianism, Monophysitism); as an independent form of monotheism in Arabia, Hanifism was widespread. Under a certain influence of these religions, in 610-612, the religious preaching of Muhammad began, initially not recognized and persecuted by the Meccans.

After the resettlement in 622g. with a small group of followers from Mecca to Medina (Hijra, which later became the starting point for the Muslim chronology, based on the lunar calendar), Muhammad now acts not only as a preacher, but also as a theocratic ruler, dictating norms of behavior in various areas of life to adherents. with every hardship comes relief. After every hardship comes relief” [94:5-6]. Verily, to those who are patient, their reward will be fully rewarded without counting” [39:10]. If Allah touches you with harm, then no one but Him will save you from it. If He wants to give you good things, then no one will turn away His mercy. He bestows it on any of His servants whom He wills. He is Forgiving, Merciful” [10:107]. “When trouble befalls them, they say: “Indeed, we belong to Allah, and to Him we will return” [2:156].

O you who believe, be patient and compete in patience, be steadfast and fear Allah, so that you may find salvation! [3:200].

In Conclusion: The original Islam is in the deeds commanded by God in the holy book, the Qur'an, and the deeds commanded by the Prophet. Today, because of ignorant and uneducated people, Islam has been misrepresented to the world, but as long as there are faithful and knowledgeable, peace-loving Muslims, the true Islam can show itself.

REFERENCES:

1. Qur`an
2. islom.uz
3. Imam Gazzoliy "The book of the heart"